

D5.5 Report on the dissemination strategy developed

WP5 Science to policy translation to stakeholders

Responsible Partner: SSI

Contributing partners: BfR, PMT members

GENERAL INFORMATION

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1. Summary

This report describes the dissemination strategy developed by WP5 of One Health EJP. The results of the One Health EJP activities are disseminated strategically, widely, timely, and in tailored ways to the relevant stakeholders; made available to be used to improve monitoring and surveillance activities, risk assessments, and risk management decision making. In this, the expression ‘results’ encompasses all outcomes that may be used by the stakeholders. Efficient uptake and use of the results maximises the impact of the research and integration activities.

2. Introduction

The overall objective of the European Joint Programme (EJP) One Health EJP (Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards, OHEJP) is to develop a European network of research institutes, mainly with reference laboratory functions. The EJP will integrate medical, veterinary, and food scientists in the field of food and feed safety in order to improve research on the prevention and control of mainly foodborne zoonoses, whilst taking into account the public health concerns of consumers and other stakeholders throughout the food chain. Following a One Health approach the EJP aims to create a sustainable European One Health framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary, and food institutes through joint programming of research agendas matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders.

One of the specific objectives of OHEJP is to exchange and communicate with national and international stakeholders, and in particular the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The OHEJP is structured into seven work packages (WP) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of One Health EJP. Work package 5 (WP5) focuses on science-to-policy translation to stakeholders, which are shown in the bottom of the figure.

Work package 5 (WP5) of OHEJP is entitled ‘Science to policy translation to stakeholders’ and it is active during the whole length of OHEJP (2018–2022, 60 months). The Lead Beneficiary is Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and the Deputy Lead Beneficiary is Statens Serum Institut (SSI). The purpose of WP5 is to establish a dialogue with ECDC and EFSA as well as EU policy makers as major stakeholders of the OHEJP and also with other relevant international stakeholders and policy makers (e.g. WHO, OIE, FAO) and national stakeholders (e.g. national ministries and the mirror groups). The needs identified by the risk-assessors will be taken into account in the procedure for updating strategic priorities defined in WP2. **WP5 functions also as a channel for the OHEJP to disseminate the results of the OHEJP to the stakeholders.** Overall, WP5 aims to

enhance the **visibility and the usefulness** of the work conducted in this EJP among policy makers and EU agencies.

The objectives of WP5 include:

- **To develop procedures for an efficient information flow and interaction between the OHEJP and stakeholders**
- **To advocate for the OHEJP and the One Health approach among stakeholders**
- To communicate to the OHEJP governing structure the research and integrative needs identified in policy processes of the European Commission and need for knowledge and integrative activities identified by the EU agencies (ECDC and EFSA)
- **To Highlight how and when procedures and data resulting from activities within the OHEJP could be used to improve policy initiatives, including risk management practices that addresses the protection of consumer health**
- To support alignment of the scientific capacity within the consortium with other similar activities in EC member states in collaboration with WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP6.
- **In collaboration with WP1, to communicate the procedures and scientific evidence based data to the EU stakeholders, the international stakeholders (WHO, OIE, FAO) and within the Member States.**

To achieve these objectives, collaboration with stakeholders has been established and procedures implemented to identify stakeholder's needs in the fields of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats (D5.1, D5.2, D5.3). This report describes the dissemination strategy: why and how the outcomes of the OHEJP activities are disseminated to the relevant stakeholders.

Dissemination is defined as follows: "The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium." (EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms).

Focus in dissemination activities is on making results available so that they can be used. Dissemination is thus disclosure of the results in an attractive and user-friendly way.

Dissemination is spreading the new knowledge as widely as possible – but in a targeted manner that focuses on target audiences that can make best use of the results. WP5 dissemination activities focus on the stakeholders.

3. Dissemination strategy to stakeholders

3.1. Target audience and objectives

Target audience of the dissemination strategy of WP5 are the stakeholders of OHEJP (D5.1) that are in a position to use the results. The WP5 actions are mainly focused on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA, DG Sante as well as national stakeholders (D5.1). However, other stakeholders are also target groups (D5.1): some of the dissemination activities are aimed at the Stakeholders Committee, some to all stakeholders. More details are provided below.

The general objective of the dissemination strategy is that OHEJP has major impact. More specifically, the objective is that the results of the OHEJP activities are timely and efficiently made available to Key EU Stakeholders so that they can be used to improve monitoring and surveillance activities, risk assessments, and risk management decision making.

3.2. Needs and expectations of the stakeholders

OHEJP is a unique interdisciplinary research community across Europe. Open and transparent dialogue between OHEJP and stakeholders ensures that OHEJP absorbs the research and integrative needs of the stakeholders and ensures the best use of the outcomes of OHEJP by the stakeholders (D5.1).

Key EU Stakeholders

The specific expectations the Key European Stakeholders have expressed to OHEJP include opportunities for feedback, receiving relevant information, and dialogue, which is maintained active throughout the duration of OHEJP. Feedback is encouraged. The research and integrative

needs of the Key EU stakeholders are actively identified (D5.2) and efficiently absorbed by the OHEJP, and lead to various actions within OHEJP. For example, during Y1 of the OHEJP, identified needs of Key EU Stakeholders were discussed, ranked, and integrated to the strategic research agenda (D5.3). They served as a major and visible input to the updated list of priority research and integrative topics (D3.6) and thus for the 2nd call for projects launched in M10 (D3.3). The Key EU Stakeholders will be consulted on the Letters of Intent, to ensure the complementarity with ongoing and recent other activities, and, in addition, this also serves to disseminate an early view of the upcoming projects. The activities and projects (JRs and JIPs) of OHEJP answer specifically to needs expressed, that is, gaps that when filled/bridged can have the highest value for informing decision-making and risk management in EU. It is important that these results are efficiently disseminated to the stakeholders.

Stakeholders Committee

Stakeholders Committee of the OHEJP is the formal structure for dialogue between the OHEJP and stakeholders. It ensures active interaction with Key EU Stakeholders and representatives of major EU funded projects to increase complementarity and to identify strategic synergies. Feedback is encouraged and actively collected at Stakeholders Committee meetings (SC meetings).

All stakeholders

Further stakeholders are encouraged to join the Stakeholders Committee and/or to follow up the EJP in other ways. The EJP wishes to show the added value this will provide to the international stakeholders WHO, OIE, and FAO.

3.3. Means

Means for collecting the information

WP5 activities to collect information for the dissemination activities will build on the work performed in WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP6 as well as active interaction within the OHEJP consortium.

Extracts of relevant scientific results as well as outcomes of integrative activities (with a focus on the One Health capacities) from deliverables and annual reports of JRPs and JIPs as well as PhD projects and summer schools may be prepared, where references to the sources will support direct interaction to research groups of interest. Similarly, extracts of scientific publications may be prepared to give a quick overview on outcomes and support immediate access to the original documents or specific researchers within the consortium.

Documents prepared during or as an outcome of workshops specifically organised to address needs of stakeholders will be important information for dissemination to stakeholders. Activities related to capacity building might also be identified through active interactions with JIPs (e.g. by participating in meetings). Moreover, all partners within the consortium will be encouraged to provide information for dissemination using a simple template (Annex 1). An additional important source will be the input received to the capacity map (D 5.4).

Means for dissemination

WP5 dissemination activities are complementary to the general dissemination activities of the OHEJP (WP1). The general dissemination activities include e.g. that scientific publications and other outcomes yielded by the OH EJP will be made available on the website of the OHEJP without delay (WP1). Stakeholders are encouraged to use these materials.

WP5 dissemination activities address specific groups: Key EU Stakeholders, Stakeholders Committee, and National stakeholders. The activities focus largely on facilitating diffusion and use of knowledge. Transactional aspects, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, are also included. Moreover, there are social change aspects: the EJP advocates OH approach by enhancing and facilitating access and use of the OH results.

In addition to the main means mentioned below, new innovative ideas for dissemination may be experimented on.

Website groups

The EJP website is taken into active use for WP5 dissemination activities. Forum groups with different level of access have been formed.

Regular tailored reports

Main structured output of dissemination activities to stakeholders are regularly compiled reports that are targeted and tailored to the stakeholders. These reports will highlight the new results the JRPs and JIPs as well as PhD projects yield, and condense the results for relevant action.

Selecting the messages to disseminate is done bottom-up. The information for the reports will be collected e.g. from the JRPs, JIPs and PhD projects from the annual reports or using a simple template (Annex 1). That is, the projects can suggest results to be highlighted and provide direct contact information to specific persons in the projects who can be contacted for further information. Focus is on results that are expected to be useful for the stakeholders. At first, the regular reports focus on Key EU Stakeholders and Stakeholders Committee (the report before SC meeting).

Meetings

The annual SC meeting is the main contact point between the Stakeholders Committee and the EJP. Another SC meeting is organized in connection to the Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM). Stakeholders are invited and welcomed to attend meetings, events and workshops of the EJP. Major dissemination activities to all stakeholders are the Annual Scientific Meetings and the Stakeholder Conference (Y5).

Dissemination activities addressing specific needs

WP5 organizes specific meetings, events, and workshops that address needs of the stakeholders. In these, experts from JRPs, JIPs and also external guests can be involved and provide specific

input for key EU stakeholders. Moreover, WP5 facilitates addressing expressed needs in several other activities of the EJP, e.g. in summer schools. Upon request, WP5 is available to suggest and send experts from the EJP to meetings, events, and workshops of the stakeholders.

Direct contacts

The Stakeholders contact list (D5.1) has two levels: the higher level is the main contact person representing each stakeholder, and the second level are the persons representing specific groups within the organisation of the stakeholder. This is to ensure efficient information flow and targeted dissemination. The list is updated and adjusted as needed (D5.1). Dissemination benefits from the snowball effect used to reach further internal and external networks of the stakeholders. WP5 serves as the main contact point for the stakeholders. Moreover, the coordinators of the JRPs and JIPs are the contact points to the specific projects, and WP3 and WP4, respectively, are the direct next level to contact if needed. The JRPs, JIPs and PhD projects are encouraged to contact WP5 proactively when interesting results are expected in the near future.

3.4. Timing

Key EU Stakeholders

WP5 is regularly in contact with the Key EU Stakeholders. The main interaction is the annual SC meeting, and in addition, another SC meeting is organized in connection to ASM. In addition, e.g., teleconferences can be organized as needed, and meetings can be planned in connection to other events. There is *ad hoc* communication as needed. The tailored reports will be compiled twice a year: by latest two months before ASM, and by latest a month before annual SC meetings, starting in 2019. This timing aims to ensure enough time for the information to reach the relevant internal structures and specific persons, and allow preparation for the ASM and SC meetings.

Stakeholders Committee

The dissemination activities to Stakeholders Committee focus on the SC meetings, and specific meetings as needed.

All stakeholders

The Stakeholder Conference in Y5 is the main dissemination activity to all stakeholders.

Annual dissemination activities to Key EU Stakeholders, SC members, and all stakeholders

	M1-M3	M4-M6	M7-M9	M10-M12
Key EU Stakeholders	TC if needed	ASM and SC meeting	TC if needed	Annual SC Meeting Y5: Stakeholders Conference
	ASM -2M report		SC Meeting -1M report	Annual report on dissemination activities
	Specific Meeting if considered relevant		Specific Meeting if considered relevant	

	M1-M3	M4-M6	M7-M9	M10-M12
Stakeholder Committee		ASM and SC meeting		Annual SC Meeting Y5: Stakeholders Conference
	Specific Meeting if considered relevant		Specific Meeting if considered relevant	

	M1-M3	M4-M6	M7-M9	M10-M12
All stakeholders		ASM		Y5: Stakeholders Conference
	Specific Meeting if considered relevant		Specific Meeting if considered relevant	

4. Evaluation and reporting

Stakeholders Committee members were consulted during the preparation of this strategy at the SC meeting 7.12.2018.

Feedback of effectiveness and other aspects of the dissemination are collected, e.g., at SC meetings.

Annual report on dissemination activities is due every December. In these reports, the dissemination activities and achievements are summarized and the plans for the coming years are described. The annual report serves as a tool for regular monitoring of the activities and their impact, and identifying needs to adjust any aspect of the strategy, including means and target audience. New innovative ideas for dissemination may be experimented on. Further stakeholders that could use the results will be identified during the years.

5. Impact and potential

Dissemination strategy is important: Efficient uptake and use of the results maximises the impact of the research.

The Key EU stakeholders are in the position to have identified which gaps, when filled or bridged, can have the highest value for informing decision-making in EU to strengthen EU resilience the most. OHEJP fills such gaps and efficient and timely dissemination of the results has major potential for impact.

Annex 1. Input for regular reports to stakeholders

WP5 of OHEJP disseminates the outcomes of the OHEJP to stakeholders. One of the means are regular reports, compiled twice a year, before ASM and related SC meeting and before the Annual Stakeholders Committee meeting. These reports highlight new results EJP activities yield, and condense the results for relevant action. In this, the expression ‘results’ encompasses all outcomes that may be interesting or useful for the stakeholders.

All EJP activities, including JRPs, JIPs and PhD projects, can suggest results to be highlighted, and provide direct contact information to specific persons in the project who can be contacted for further information. A form on the One Health EJP website might be used to collect this information. Focus is on results that are expected to be useful for the stakeholders. All activities within EJP are encouraged to actively use this opportunity. In addition, contacting WP5 directly at any time is encouraged.

Title of the activity or project, type (JRP, JIP, PhD project, other)
Results wished to be disseminated to stakeholders
Brief description of why these results are expected to be interesting to or useful for the stakeholders
Contact information